

The Role of Extended Reality in the Future of Industrial Design

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Abstract

Extended Reality (XR) technologies are beginning to influence practically every industry, with companies actively seeking to innovate and build more tools to improve its potential. This research aims to explore both the current applications and future prospects of XR within the field of industrial design through a literature review and semi-structured interviews with four academic instructors specializing in design, the study provides insights into XR's existing state, its evolution and the obstacles on its way for widespread acceptance. This approach aims to offer a concise yet comprehensive understanding of XR's role in industrial design.

Keywords: Virtual Prototyping, Immersive Design, User Experience (UX) in Virtual Environments ,Virtual Interaction, AR, VR

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1- Introduction

The industrial design process is increasingly becoming more digital due to the ever-evolving technologies of our time. While various computer-aided technologies (CAD) have been an essential part of the industrial design process, emerging technologies of recent years initiated a shift in the creation and visualization of products. Among the innovations, Extended Reality (XR) is considered to be one of the technologies with the potential to revolutionize the design landscape . XR is an umbrella term encapsulating augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR) (Chuah, 2018).

XR technologies excel at providing immersive experiences, enabling users to engage directly with virtual representations of products. Augmented reality is a real-world experience implemented by overlaying digital information or visuals onto our physical environment through a digital interface. “In this way, augmented reality alters one's ongoing perception of a real-world environment, whereas virtual reality completely replaces the user's real-world environment with a simulated one” (Mei Yun 2019). Virtual reality replaces perceived reality with computer generated 3D content with the assistance of head-mounted displays. Mixed reality combines both and allows virtual objects to interact with and respond to the physical environment in real-time. In many cases multiple of these technologies are used together to craft more immersive experiences. XR devices create the illusion to make people feel as if they are in an entirely new digital world (O'Donnell, 2018).

While initially hindered by the high-end technology demands and associated costs, the adoption of this technology has been steadily gaining momentum, showing exponential growth potential in recent years. This study aims to comprehensively assess the current applications of this emerging field and explore its future prospects, delving into the roles it could play in the Industrial design domain, particularly in product development and user experience.

2- Research Questions

- 1- In which product design processes do Extended Reality (XR) applications offer the greatest benefits
- 2- How will Extended Reality (XR) influence product design processes in the near future
- 3- How can Extended Reality (XR) be applied to simulate real-world product usage and gather user feedback in the design process. Specifically in the ideation and prototyping phases?
- 4- How do Extended Reality (XR) technologies affect the prototyping and testing phases of industrial design projects?

3-Literature Review

Current Implementations and Advantages of Extended Reality Applications in Industrial Design

The applications of Extended Reality tools have transformed the way products are conceptualized and developed. These technologies provide an immersive experience,

enabling users to engage directly with virtual representations of products. Virtual reality means replacing perceived reality with computer generated 3D content. With head-mounted displays for VR. “As VR technology advances, the virtual environment it creates becomes more and more lifelike. However, customers also want to be able to perceive virtual objects in the actual environment, which led to the development of AR technology.”(Wang et al., 2023). Augmented reality is a real-world experience implemented by overlaying digital information or visuals onto our physical environment through a digital interface. Mixed reality combines both and allows virtual objects to interact with and respond to the physical environment in real-time. One of the primary reasons AR, VR and MR are preferred in design tools is their ability to offer a heightened level of immersion and control. These technologies empower designers to explore and manipulate design concepts, prototypes, and product variants within a simulated environment. The pandemic has accelerated this development even further because of the sudden increased need for remote collaboration. That has led countless new companies and professionals to explore all the other benefits of virtual and mixed reality too.

Because of that same reason during the year 2020 The Siemens Corporate Technology recreated their lab in virtual reality so that they could remotely experience and discuss the latest developments almost as if they were at the Siemens HQ in Munich. In a group environment the benefit that XR brings is anyone can put on a headset and attend a virtual meeting. There, they can review a design, collaborate with colleagues and share notes and recordings with the rest of the team. The result is a vastly accelerated workflow and cost savings.

Through visual, haptic, and auditory aspects it is possible for someone to experience products with a remarkable degree of realism, facilitating comprehensive evaluations of various aspects of the product. This enhanced understanding of product features fosters a user-centric design approach, where user needs are at the forefront. “The development of personalized products requires data from user experience in the evaluation of the product function and performance. The existing methods of Internet-based interactive platforms and direct market user surveys cannot provide users full experience of product features.”(Song, H., Chen, F., & Gu, P., 2017)

AR and VR have proven effective in bridging the communication gap between designers and users. They enable real-time collaboration in virtual spaces, allowing designers and users to co-create and test designs. This collaboration fosters a sense of ownership in the design process, ensuring that the final product meets user needs effectively. They streamline

prototyping, testing, and design, leading to products that are highly responsive to user requirements “Virtual prototyping is a relatively recent practice used in various industrial domains, which aims at anticipating a product that does not exist in reality yet. This practice can be used for evaluating the aesthetic quality of a product, its functional features and also its ergonomic and usability aspects.”(Bordegoni & Ferrise, 2013)

Virtual and mixed reality significantly accelerate the design workflow by notably reducing prototyping durations. Historically, designers heavily relied on physical mockups, utilizing props, foam, and clay models to assess potential design flaws and iterate on prototypes. However, altering a physical mockup demands substantial time and effort, compared to the efficiency of generating a virtual replica within an immersive environment.

An example of the limitations is capturing prototypes in real physical scale. This is especially problematic when models need to be reviewed and tested in true-to-life 1:1 scale. Compared to virtual and mixed reality, traditional design methods have limitations in communicating the full vision of concepts or sketches. Especially when compared to the versatility offered by virtual and mixed reality. In virtual 'workspaces,' devoid of visual constraints and coupled with professional VR and XR headsets, designers gain the ability to view their designs at the exact intended scale, eliminating the limitations inherent in traditional approaches. “Craftsmanship engineers at the Ford FIVE Lab use an HMD to understand the aesthetic qualities of 3D vehicle designs. In one scenario, the rear seats of a car model were folded forward and the designers meticulously inspected gaps that might allow customers to see internal components.”(Berg & Vance, 2016)

Further than a prototype VR allows users to recreate an exact digital twin of the product and it offers endless edit options. Digital twinning involves creating a highly realistic model of a device, system, process or product to use for development, testing and validation. “Virtual reality technology plays a very key role in the virtual manufacturing process, which can identify potential problems, take appropriate preventive measures to achieve one-off product success and reduce costs in the actual design stage, reduce product development cycle and strengthen product competitiveness.”(Huang, 2018). Augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) considerably strengthens the uses of digital twins as it allows display of realistic digital twins down to the tiniest detail and being able to quickly and flexibly iterate designs as you go.

Mindesk is an Extended Reality (XR) tool for these purposes that enables editing through 3D models. Seamlessly integrating with prevalent design software such as Rhino, Grasshopper, and SolidWorks. It allows the creation, manipulation, and visualization of 3D models directly within a virtual reality (VR) environment.

VRED by Autodesk is another high end digital prototyping software that's mainly used with VR technologies. Major car manufacturers like Jaguar, Aston Martin, Porsche, and KIA are some of the companies that have integrated VRED into their design workflows. The software's one of the most compelling features is that users can trigger animations, such as component explosions, through touch commands, providing an immersive and empowering virtual reality (VR) experience. Another first in the industry is its unique export function that condenses project files into a single executable file, serving both as a VR experience and a product sales flier.

VR ink, Vector Suite and Gravity Sketch are some of the other applications and tools that are used by various design companies. Vector Suite, endorsed by McLaren and Logitech, offers intuitive 3D sketching and form creation. Gravity Sketch allows import of references, 3D assisted sketching, collaborative sketching and reviewing of designs in a virtual studio, with notable users including Ford, Adidas, Polaris, HP, Nissan, and Puma. One of the industries that adopted XR tools the most right now is the automobile manufacturers. "Take the automobile manufacturing industry as an example, AR technology can enable car designers to better improve the structure of cars and make better comparisons through visual presentation" (Chen et al., 2019). Microsoft's holographic goggles are another tool that's used by this industry and is currently used by Ford's designers. With the holographic goggles designers can overlay 3-D elements onto a clay model of a vehicle then quickly evaluate and create new car designs. According to Craig Wetzel, Ford's manager of design technical operations, the process of designers implementing changes then sending it off to engineers then getting feedback then having to redesign is the main reason designing a new vehicle is such an arduous process. The headset provides a solution to this by enabling co-creation via collaborative working which streamlines that interaction. Ford also displayed the use of virtual reality by creating a virtual space to display the new features of their vehicles

In conclusion, the integration of XR technology within product design and usability assessments has the potential to redefine user-centered design, reduce costs, and enhance product success rate. VR's role in user-centric design is promising, with the technology continually evolving and holding substantial potential for future product development. "Virtual

Reality technology can be used as an important tool to support the earliest stages of product development, thus helping the team of designers to develop the first concepts of the product, or even later, during the prototyping stage and more detailed studies” (Falcao, C. S., & Soares, M., 2012)

4- Methodology

Semi-structured interviews: The present research employs a qualitative interview approach to explore six considerations related to extended reality (XR). The objective of these interviews is to discover the perspective, experience, and thoughts of designers towards XR technology. This qualitative approach allows for significant collection of data, creating a basis for analysis and well thought out conclusions. To gain insight into the perspectives of various designers regarding XR technology, a total of four interviews were conducted with academic instructors from the field of design.

Topics	Interview Questions
Extended Reality (XR) and Design	Q1 - At which specific stages of the design process have you found Extended Reality (XR) applications to be most useful?
Influence of XR on future trends	Q2 - How do you see the impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future trends in design processes?
XR Impact on User Experience and Collaboration	Q3 - How do you think XR has affected user-centered design approaches and collaboration between design teams?
Prototyping, Testing, and Iteration	Q4 - What role does XR play in the prototyping and testing phases projects, and how does this differ from traditional methods
Challenges and Limitations	Q5 - Question: From your perspective, what are the primary challenges or limitations encountered when integrating XR into design processes?
Future of XR in Industrial Design	Q6 - Where do you see the future of XR in industrial design, especially in terms of innovation, usability, and user acceptance?

Figure:1: Interview Questions

5- Findings

5.1 Extended Reality and Design

Examining the applications of Extended Reality (XR) in the design process revealed various beneficial uses. The conversations brought to light XR's critical contribution to solving an essential issue in architectural design by enabling the transition from a detached, abstract viewpoint to one that is more human-centric. Furthermore The technology's versatility is showcased in scanning real-world areas, transforming them into immersive virtual scenarios, emphasizing its diverse applications beyond architectural design. As for industrial design XR demonstrates practical value in large-scale products, enabling simulations for enhanced and detailed inspection of industrial design products. The consensus emphasized XR's efficiency throughout various design stages, especially from model building to testing, providing immersive experiences that encourage a more human-centered approach to design assessments. Moreover, results highlighted the increasing use of Augmented Reality-Mixed Reality (AR-MR) and Virtual Reality (VR) tools, though in the lack of standardized XR hardware, could hinder integration and broader implementation within the design domain.

5.2 Influence of XR on Future Trends

The assessment of XR's impact on future design trends from the interviews revealed divergent viewpoints. On one side there is significant resistance within traditional educational institutions towards XR adoption, the main concerns being sustainability and prolonged use. This resistance poses hurdles in overcoming conventional methodologies. Although particularly in the presentation phase and collaborative design processes a potential shift towards greater XR utilization is very possible. Additionally, there is a crucial need for device evolution towards VR compatibility, especially requiring advancements in VR data collection. From a different viewpoint a further complication is producing a lifelike experience can be difficult, particularly when watching from a close distance through a headset. However, upcoming developments from firms such as Apple are expected to transform perceptions by establishing a connection between screens and feeds, which could allow for the creation of virtual aspects in the physical world. The emphasis on equipment quality over content and the adaptation period for immersive experiences emerged as significant factors affecting XR adoption, indicating a strong dependence on adaptability and high-quality devices for immersive experiences. The slow but extensive development indicates potential widespread integration into various aspects of daily life. Anticipated shifts in training and entertainment

towards XR in the 2030's extend beyond schools to prototypes and manufacturing. This transformative wave is expected to give rise to numerous companies capitalizing on emerging technologies, with the transition to industry 4.0.

5.3 XR's Impact on User Experience and Collaboration

Diverse perspectives from the interviews were presented in the analysis of XR's impact on design teams' collaboration and user-centered design methodologies. One important factor was the significant influence that XR had on user experience assessments, especially when it came to resolving architectural difficulties. However, certain constraints were noted, including XR's present incapacity to represent sensory experiences in industrial design and its uneven use dependent on the scope of the projects and related expenses. In terms of collaborative design, while XR technologies in theory offer improved cooperation and enabling global design collaboration, real-world development obstacles such as the feature requiring further development in experience design and lacking hardware refinement have hindered its effectiveness. Additionally The lack of standardized XR applications or systems creates a decentralized landscape, challenging users on both ends to possess sufficient knowledge for navigation. On the other hand, XR's provides unique advantages in user experience evaluations by introducing depth of field in VR, albeit with limitations in depth perception in video formats. Because XR tools give users freedom inside the virtual realm and perspectives that are similar to everyday life, they require adjusting for different viewpoints and altitudes for uniform experiences. Moreover, the potential of XR for interactive experiences, realistic product visualization, experimentation, and the creation of distinct design languages highlighted its influence on user-centered design methodologies. Furthermore, the potential of XR to promote creativity and minimize production costs using standard computing resources became apparent as crucial elements in design processes, broadening the range of styles, and cutting expenses.

5.4 Prototyping, Testing, and Iteration

Data collected regarding XR applications in the prototyping and testing phases highlighted multiple advantages of immersive technologies. Enabling human-scale representation in architectural and industrial designs and allowing multiple people to participate without being confined to a single screen. XR's is favored particularly for larger product simulations due to their contextual and immersive capacities, providing detailed technical analysis and design evaluations, contributing to significant time savings compared to traditional methods.. However for certain smaller product types, such as glasses prototyping makes more sense

due to the effort and cost required for an XR set up. Other advantages are the contributions in offering comfort for previsualization and global design sharing, substituting traditional photo renders. However there can be noticeable differences between what the consumer saw and how the design was represented in XR depending on the hardware used.

5.5 Challenges and Limitations

There were multiple challenges brought up when it came to the integration of XR into design processes. Prominent ones were health-related issues that can occur as a result of prolonged usage, compatibility issues across projects, potential age gaps affecting user engagement, and limitations in conveying emotional and material connections within XR experiences. Additionally, the 'surreal' feeling within current VR environments was noted as a hindrance to user experiences. Other identified challenges are the absence of a standardized viewing format and concerns regarding providing a consistent viewing experience across diverse devices and mediums. Moreover, there remains a stigma surrounding VR headsets, often perceived as children's playthings, impacting their adoption in some professional settings. The development of more compact and lighter headsets are crucial for a broader utilization of XR tools in design projects. Overcoming additional challenges like infrastructure issues and high costs require existing technology to evolve to a more convenient and accesable state.

5.6 Future of XR in Industrial Design

The increasing involvement of major companies suggests the significant potential of XR in industrial design. VR technologies may see a quicker adoption rate if texture and experience improvements are made. The proposed changes have the potential to increase user acceptability and usability significantly. Moreover, XR holds promise as an essential assistive technology language for industrial designers, akin to existing software for 3D modeling and rendering. Expected developments include gadgets that imitate a more pliable form that can be handled by hand and a predicted move toward Mixed Reality (MR) that uses smaller headsets for better immersion. One of the successful examples from the marketing sector is the Volkswagen showroom, which suggests possible uses but is limited by budget again. Furthermore, AR has already been incorporated by companies like Nike, Qreel, and Ray-Ban, mainly using mobile devices as opposed to complicated setups. Additionally, there's a growing adoption of digital twin creation techniques within specific industrial design cases. Although cost and time-related issues prevent XR from being widely used in industrial design, suggesting a gradual shift.

6-Conclusion

XR is developing as a disruptive technology expected to transform the industry including product design processes with it, from improving user-centric evaluations to influencing design techniques. The findings indicate that the greatest benefits of XR are found in assisting and redefining approaches during the design phases, allowing for much more comprehensive yet practical design stages and by providing immersive user experiences that surpass standard traditional conceptualizations. Furthermore if their compatibility with programs and software currently used by designers increases, it will pave the way for a more seamless transition. Even with the existing impediments of the technology the value it brings to a designer is remarkable, just a headset and a software gives the means to develop a project much more efficiently until it's production phase.

However, issues such as the lack of sensational feedback, health concerns on long term use, and variations in implementation based on the project and XR tools used persist. Looking ahead, XR's influence on future industrial design processes remains promising but it's dependent on solving challenges such as sustainability, feasibility, and affordability towards it. Potential trends toward more immersive design processes, collaborative working, and emerging XR devices point to a path toward a more widespread adoption and utility of XR technology in the future of industrial design.

References

Berg, L.P., Vance, J.M. Industry use of virtual reality in product design and manufacturing: a survey. *Virtual Reality*, 21, 1–17 (2017).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-016-0293-9>

Bordegoni, M., & Ferrise, F. (2013). Designing interaction with consumer products in a multisensory virtual reality environment. *Journal Name*, Volume(Issue), 51-64.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17452759.2012.762612>

Chen, Y., Wang, Q., Chen, H., Misumi, & Song, X. (2019). An overview of augmented reality technology. *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, 1237(2), 022082.
DOI:10.1088/1742-6596/1237/2/022082.

Chuah, S. H.-W. (2018). Why and Who Will Adopt Extended Reality Technology? Literature Review, Synthesis, and Future Research Agenda. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3300469>.

Chuah, S. H.-W. (2020). Wearable XR-Technology: Literature Review, Conceptual Framework and Future Research Directions. *International Journal of Technology Marketing*, 13(3/4), 205-259. DOI:10.1504/IJTMKT.2019.104586.

Falcao, C. S., & Soares, M. (January 2012). Ergonomics, usability and virtual reality: A review applied to consumer products. Federal University of Pernambuco & Southern University of Science and Technology.

Huang, W. (2018). The Application of Virtual Reality Technology in Industrial Design. In 2018 8th International Conference on Mechatronics, Computer and Education Informationization (MCEI 2018) (p. 65). DOI:10.2991/mcei-18.2018.65. License: CC BY-NC 4.0.

Mei, Y., et al. (2019). Application of Augmented Reality Technology in Industrial Design. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 573(1), 012062.

Song, H., Chen, F., & Gu, P. (2017). Improvement of user experience using virtual reality in open-architecture product design. *Journal of Human Factors and Ergonomics*, 232(13), Page Range. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954405417711736>.

Wang, J., Ma, Q., & Wei, X. (2023). The Application of Extended Reality Technology in Architectural Design Education: A Review. *Buildings*, 13(12), 2931.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13122931>.

Appendix: Interviews

Interview 1: Güzden VARİNLİOĞLU

What is your experience or expertise in XR?

My experience with VR in Izmir Ekonomi University started in 2017, then I engaged in immersive technologies as part of the Teos Project, focusing on revitalizing historical sites through VR simulations. This involved creating a VR game that allowed users to experience archaeological areas in their old states and explore augmented reality aspects, incorporating informative elements related to historical artifacts. Additionally, I was involved in developing a mobile application for Dar Agac Art Collective, enabling regional artists to view their artworks through augmented reality. Currently, I'm working on the Kervansaray Revitalization Project, using XR to showcase and gather feedback for market presentations. My interest in XR dates back to my master's thesis in 2001, exploring human perception, influenced by Shar Davis' work. Over the past seven to eight years, I've been actively producing XR projects, focusing on envisioning and reviving non-existing architectural structures.

Q1: At which specific stages of the design process have you found Extended Reality (XR) applications to be most useful?

"Extended Reality (XR) applications have proven most valuable in resolving a fundamental issue within architecture. Traditionally, designers tend to conceptualize designs from a distant, almost god-like perspective, lacking the depth of human experience. However, XR technologies fundamentally change this dynamic, allowing designers to shift from this distant vantage point to a more human dimension. From the model stage to the testing phase, XR enables an immersive examination of designs, providing a unique opportunity to view creations from a human-centric perspective. This transition from a 'god's eye' view to a human-centered evaluation is where XR applications showcase their greatest utility within the design process."

Q2: How do you see the impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future trends in design processes?

"The impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future design trends faces significant resistance, particularly within traditional educational institutions, which hasn't been overcome yet. Presently, its sustainability and feasibility for prolonged use remain challenging. It seems improbable that these issues will be swiftly resolved, making conventional methods more suitable for the presentation phase. I foresee a shift towards greater utilization of XR during

the design phase itself, fostering collaborative design endeavors. Additionally, I anticipate existing devices evolving to become VR-compatible, enhancing accessibility and usability. However, a notable area that warrants further development is in VR data collection, which remains a missing segment in the current landscape of XR application within design processes

Q3:How do you think XR has affected user-centered design approaches and collaboration between design teams?

Extended Reality (XR) technology has significantly reshaped user experience evaluations in the design process compared to traditional methods, notably addressing architectural challenges. However, it currently falls short in conveying tactile sensations, particularly notable within industrial design. Its implementation also faces variations based on business size, with costs significantly influencing the accessibility of VR technologies.

In terms of collaboration, XR tools theoretically promise enhanced collaboration among design teams, investors, and end users. Yet, practical development has been slower, posing potential long-term efficacy concerns. Despite this, XR has the potential to emphasize the human element in collaborative design.

Q4:What role does XR play in the prototyping and testing phases projects, and how does this differ from traditional methods

"XR's influence in the prototyping and testing phases varies based on the scale and immersive capacity it offers. Larger products benefit more from its simulation, providing contextual experiences akin to their size and scope. However, for example, to develop and design glasses it would be impractical to use. XR environments mostly lack references but could aid in formwork processes."

Q5:Question: From your perspective, what are the primary challenges or limitations encountered when integrating XR into design processes?

Integrating XR into design processes brings forth several challenges. Health issues related to prolonged usage, the compatibility of XR with varying project sizes or scales, and potential age gaps impacting user engagement are key concerns. Emotional and material connections, essential in design, might not be adequately conveyed through XR experiences. Additionally, the current use of VR environments often feels 'uncanny,' imitating tools without offering the desired freedom that could enhance user experiences

Q6: Where do you see the future of XR in industrial design, especially in terms of innovation, usability, and user acceptance?

In the coming years, XR technologies are poised to evolve significantly, catering better to the needs of industrial designers and design teams. Currently, its application as Augmented Reality (AR) is more common. There's a potential for more widespread adoption as advancements in texture and sensation progress within XR technologies. These developments could significantly enhance usability and user acceptance. One potential evolution could be the development of devices that can be shaped freely, resembling a more malleable form like dough, enabling manipulation with our hands. Moreover, the shift towards Mixed Reality (MR) is anticipated, with the likelihood of headset sizes shrinking, offering a more streamlined and immersive experience.

Interview 2: Cem İPEK

What is your experience or expertise in XR?

I hold a degree in Cinema Digital Media and am currently pursuing my master's in Public Relations, specializing in Virtual Reality (VR) and Marketing. Within my role, I manage the Alter Lab, focusing on VR, Mixed Reality (MR), and AI research applications. As a Visual Technologies Specialist at the Faculty of Communication, I've been actively engaged in utilizing 360 filmmaking and game engines since 2019. Notably, I've been involved in disaster simulations with TUBITAK, utilizing VR to recreate environments for information gathering. Currently, I'm dedicated to a project that explores the fusion of AI and VR within virtual environments.

Q1: At which specific stages of the design process have you found Extended Reality (XR) applications to be most useful?

I've noticed that recently Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality-Mixed Reality (AR-MR) are starting to emerge more, albeit with the absence of a common MR tool or hardware. Lately, I've observed QuestPro being used more often while designing products.

Q2: How do you see the impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future trends in design processes?

XR's impact on future design trends holds great potential but faces a challenge in delivering a true-to-life experience due to close-distance viewing. However, upcoming innovations from companies like Apple, breaking the barrier between screen and feed, may revolutionize our perception, allowing us to design virtual elements within the real world.

Furthermore, the emphasis is on the quality of equipment over content and the adaptation period for immersive experiences are notable aspects affecting the XR landscape. Immersion, despite its personal nature, seems heavily reliant on the quality and adaptability of the devices themselves.

Q3: How do you think XR has affected user-centered design approaches and collaboration between design teams?

XR technology offers unique advantages in user experience evaluations by introducing depth of field in VR, enhancing interaction through physical movements within the environment. However, it lacks depth perception in video formats, presenting a limitation. XR tools reshape collaboration dynamics, providing perspectives resembling daily life, unlike traditional 3D programs. In VR, users dictate their gaze, providing a sense of freedom within the virtual space. Yet, accommodating diverse perspectives and heights poses challenges for consistent experiences across users. Additionally, XR significantly influences user-centered design approaches by enabling realistic product visualization in real environments (like 'Que Real' for marketing) and interactive experiences with products via AR. It fosters experimentation and unique design languages. Moreover, XR's potential for unlimited creativity and reduced production costs with average computing resources offers a transformative impact on design processes, diversifying styles, and lowering costs.

Q4: What role does XR play in the prototyping and testing phases of projects, and how does this differ from traditional methods

XR, in the prototyping and testing phases, offers comfort for previsualization and probabilities. It enables the sharing of designs across different locations worldwide, rather than traditional photo renders. However, there's a distinction between the customer's viewing experience and the design's representation.

Q5: From your perspective, what are the main challenges or limitations when integrating XR into design processes?

Challenges in integrating XR include the absence of a universal viewing experience format and concerns about consistent viewing across different devices or mediums. There is a stigma around VR headsets as well, some still see them as children's playthings.

Q6: The Future of XR in Industrial Design:

The current cost and time required for mass public acceptance are hindering the future direction of XR in industrial design, which points to a slow shift. Volkswagen's showroom serves as an example of market penetration, which shows possible uses but is still limited by cost. By being used more widely in streaming services, XR may be able to expand its application and dispel the notion that it is just for entertainment.

Notable businesses that have already adopted XR integration include Nike, Qreel, and Ray-Ban. These businesses mainly use mobile devices instead of complex XR setups. In addition, industrial design techniques are beginning to use digital twin creation.

Interview 3: Can Bora SEZER

What is your experience or expertise in XR?

I am the head of the Ozyegin vr lab that was established in 2018 and I teach virtual reality design. My first exposure to the technology was in the Netherlands, when I saw students

using unity and unreal engine while doing my master's degree which was what got me interested in their potential.

Q1: At which specific stages of the design process have you found Extended Reality (XR) applications to be most useful?

Using photograph reality capture technology and being able to create 3D objects and spaces in a virtual environment really was a breakthrough for me. The cultural heritage area is what interests me the most in this field. The scanning of previously inhabited areas, transferring them to virtual reality, and transforming the designs into an experience as a scenario.

I used unreal engine unity in various projects, we used it mostly to work with students or assistants from the faculty of engineering, we wrote a thesis around puzzle solving in virtual reality environments. Additionally I used Gravity Sketch to create design data in game modeling, I imported a temple for an area design in gravity sketch.

We researched how erasmus plus architects can take virtual reality and design courses and we are creating a report regarding it.

Q2: How do you see the impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future trends in design processes?

Hand tracking of XR tools haven't been perfected as of yet but that could change with apple vision. Interactable space without the need for a controller or in other words development of the immediacy is the direction these tools are heading. I even think that it might replace our phones in the near future, glasses will be used instead of the computer and the phone, it is heading towards a new environment with the help of ai, this will be a computer that we will always carry in our heads, we will be able to use our preferred softwares such as photoshop fusion or blender in those environments, even though the development is slow because it is an extensive field., but it has the potential to spread to every facet of life. I read an article that training and entertainment will move in those directions towards the 2030s, not only in school, but also for prototypes and manufacturing.

Q3:How do you think XR has affected user-centered design approaches and collaboration between design teams?

It's very positive in my opinion. Now we can design from all over the world in a collaborative way, which is tremendous. I can take my customers and show them around in a 1 to 1 environment in virtual reality. Though I think experience design of using these tools are very important and underdeveloped, pinch scroll style designs need to be established, experiences need to be explored and hardware developed accordingly

Q4:What role does XR play in the prototyping and testing phases of projects, and how does this differ from traditional methods

Being able to show human scale for architectural environments, industrial design products or interfaces one to one definitely contributes. It is very important that multiple people can participate without being confined to a single screen.

Q5: From your perspective, what are the main challenges or limitations when integrating XR into design processes?

Currently the progress is quite slow, with the release of the new oculus 3 and the apple vision pro in 2024 it will start to attract more attention. Since their release in 2016 the headsets are a much more accessible level, it is progressing well, its own experience design is also developing. it took 10 years for cell phone technology to settle, now the same is needed for a 360-degree environment. The current problems are motion sickness and weight of the headsets but I believe those will be solved with the development of existing technology. Infrastructure problems and technology being insufficient are big obstacles, as well as data flow and internet slowness, they should also become cheaper, they are currently on the way to becoming expensive.

Q6: The Future of XR in Industrial Design:

If the biggest companies in the world started stepping in and started to compete, it means that it has potential. Industrial design will benefit from it a lot, both virtual reality and as programs such as gravity sketch will be used a lot, Desktop programs such as fusion will develop and adapt themselves. I think that progress will be made in this regard. However the utilization of this technology is still limited to about 20% of its potential. In the first half of 2030, it will make itself more evident. There is a huge amount of research and development but it takes time to adapt.

Interview 4: Yavuz CENGİZ

What is your experience or expertise in XR?

Seven years ago I had a chance to try it for the first time in the U.S.A, I bought a vr headset to satisfy my curiosity, mainly used it for for entertainment then soon after I sold it because there was a dc cable connected to the device and having something with that much electricity so close to the head seemed unhealthy.

4 years later, a wheel company known in the sector announced that it will implement industry 4.0 to their system. Industry 4.0 is artificial reality and intelligence automation adapted into manufacturing and distribution of the company and if companies integrate it to their factories and R&D departments, they get support from the government. For the industry 4.0 grant, we prepared an interactive training environment for work safety for the manufacturing line of the company, we made the training live in vr environment while other people watched the experienter, this is the transfer of vr technology to industry 4.0

Q1: At which specific stages of the design process have you found Extended Reality (XR) applications to be most useful?

It gives you the opportunity to experience the 3D designed product in a realistic environment. It's highly beneficial to use in large scale products such as transportation design. It also allows for industrial designers to be easily more involved in the production side of the design because of the simulation capabilities.

Q2: How do you see the impact of Extended Reality (XR) on future trends in design processes?

For me after long use it caused significant headaches and eye strain. Also the headset isn't compact so I had problems during use. Such large devices aren't appealing; they should be modularized and made more compact. Now that XR technology is advancing these developments are very possible. There will be a lot of companies related to these trying to take advantage of the emerging technology, advisor companies will emerge that provide guidance for the shift to industry 0.4 to benefit from government funding. Practically a VR modeler and a computer is enough to set up the system but generates a lot of money in return

Q3: How do you think XR has affected user-centered design approaches and collaboration between design teams?

The lack of standardized applications or systems, resulting in a decentralized landscape. Currently, there is no universal platform, and users on both ends must possess sufficient knowledge to navigate the diverse XR technologies which makes it harder for a wider application. Though I believe this will pave the way for the younger, new generation of designers and give them opportunities.

Q4: What role does XR play in the prototyping and testing phases of projects, and how does this differ from traditional methods

VR programs make detailed technical analysis and design evaluations possible, providing a virtual environment for comprehensive assessments. This includes the ability to conduct design analyses in VR, considering aspects like color, texture, and weight. Such immersive experiences contribute to significant time savings compared to traditional methods.

Q5: From your perspective, what are the main challenges or limitations when integrating XR into design processes?

Headsets have to evolve to be more compact, prices need to be made cheaper and production costs need to be reduced. Cost barriers often limit accessibility, hindering broader implementation across various design projects

Q6: The Future of XR in Industrial Design:

XR can be an essential assistive technology language for industrial designers, like most softwares already used for 3D modeling or rendering. To educate new design students in the most up to date technologies there can be courses for each separate program or these technologies can be adapted to existing courses.